

THE STAGES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING METHOD

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the development of project-based learning method, generally, at schools and lyceums that allows pupils and students to learn through hands-on experiences and active participation. Being considered as a student-centred method that encourages critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and creativity, it involves students working on a project over an extended period of time that engages them in solving a real-world problem or answering a complex question.*

Keywords: *project-based learning, teaching approach, real-world challenges, collaboration, real-world projects, data.*

Project-based learning (PBL) is a teaching method and a dynamic and engaging approach to education that allows students to learn by doing. It's all about giving them real-world challenges to tackle, allowing them to apply their knowledge and skills in a practical way. In other words, it's like taking a deep dive into a topic, exploring it from different angles, and creating something meaningful. To be precise, instead of just memorizing facts about the solar system, students could design and build a model of a rocket that could travel to Mars. This kind of project encourages them to research, collaborate, problem-solve, and even present their findings to others.

PBL is a student-centered approach where learning happens through hands-on, real-world projects. Instead of focusing on memorizing facts and figures, students delve into complex challenges, research, collaborate, and create solutions.

The project starts with a real-world problem or question that students need to solve. This could be anything from designing a sustainable city to creating a marketing campaign for a new product. Students dive into research to gather information, analyze data, and develop a plan for tackling the challenge. Students work together in teams, sharing ideas, brainstorming solutions, and creating their project. Once the project is complete, students present their findings and reflect on what they learned. This could be in the form of a report, presentation, or even a demonstration.

By involving scientists in the development of PBL, educators can create more authentic, engaging, and impactful learning experiences for students. This collaboration helps bridge the gap between scientific research and education, fostering a deeper understanding of science and its role in solving real-world problems.

Project-based learning (PBL) has evolved over time, reflecting changes in educational philosophies and the increasing emphasis on real-world learning. Here's a look at the key stages in its development:

Early Roots (19th Century)

John Dewey, a prominent American philosopher and educator, played a pivotal role in shaping the progressive education movement. Dewey advocated for learning through experience, problem-solving, and active engagement. Progressive educators believed that students should be

active participants in their learning, rather than passive recipients of information. They emphasized student agency, allowing students to explore their interests and develop their own understanding.

The "Project Method": The concept of project-based learning emerged in the late 19th century, influenced by the progressive education movement. John Dewey, a prominent educator, advocated for learning through experience and problem-solving. The "Project Method" laid the foundation for modern PBL, emphasizing the importance of hands-on learning, student agency, and real-world applications.

Early PBL projects often involved hands-on activities, like building models, conducting experiments, or creating art projects. Moreover, these activities encouraged students to tackle real-world problems, such as building a model house, conducting a scientific experiment, or creating a piece of art. The focus was primarily on individual student projects, with less emphasis on collaboration. Projects encouraged students to ask questions, research, and explore their own understanding. [2;83]

While the PBL of the 19th century had its limitations, it represented a significant step towards a more engaging and relevant approach to education. It paved the way for the development of more structured and collaborative PBL approaches that continue to evolve today.

Mid-20th Century: The Rise of Curriculum-Based PBL

The mid-20th century was a pivotal period in the development of project-based learning (PBL). This era saw PBL become more structured and integrated with the curriculum, moving beyond its early, more experimental roots.

In the mid-20th century, PBL projects began to be more carefully designed to align with specific learning objectives and curriculum standards. This ensured that students were acquiring the knowledge and skills outlined in the curriculum. Projects began to emphasize inquiry-based learning, encouraging students to ask questions, research, and develop their own understanding. Projects were often tailored to specific subjects, such as history, science, or literature, allowing students to delve deeper into particular areas of study. Teachers played a more active role in planning and guiding PBL projects, ensuring that they were aligned with curriculum goals and provided appropriate scaffolding for students. Projects encouraged students to ask questions, formulate hypotheses, and conduct research, fostering a spirit of inquiry and critical thinking and, consequently, students learned to gather information from various sources, analyze data, and draw conclusions, developing valuable research skills.

Later, PBL projects began to incorporate multiple subjects, allowing students to see how different disciplines connect and apply their knowledge in a more holistic way. To be more precise, interdisciplinary projects often addressed real-world issues, such as environmental problems, social justice, or technological advancements, making learning more relevant and engaging.

The mid-20th century saw the emergence of new technologies, such as computers, which began to be incorporated into PBL projects. Students could use computers for research, data analysis, and presentation, enhancing their learning experience and preparing them for the digital age. Technology opened up new possibilities for PBL, allowing for more complex projects and a wider range of learning experiences.

Late 20th Century: The Emergence of Collaborative PBL

This period is known as the era where PBL truly embraced collaboration as a central element. This shift was fueled by several factors, including: The late 20th century witnessed a significant shift towards collaborative PBL, recognizing the importance of teamwork and

communication in the workplace. Projects began to incorporate multiple subjects, fostering a more holistic learning experience. The advent of technology opened up new possibilities for PBL, allowing students to use digital tools for research, creation, and presentation.

Constructivist learning theory emphasized that knowledge is not passively received but actively constructed through social interaction and collaboration. This theory encouraged educators to create learning environments where students could work together, share ideas, and build knowledge collectively. PBL became a powerful tool for implementing constructivist learning principles, as it naturally fostered collaboration and dialogue among students [1;67]. The technology was an implemented tool in the effectiveness of PBL, online collaboration tools, such as Google Docs and shared workspaces, made it easier for students to work together on projects, regardless of their physical location. These tools facilitated communication, information sharing, and the development of shared understanding, enhancing collaboration within PBL projects. Technology enabled students to collaborate with peers from around the world, expanding their perspectives and fostering global citizenship. Projects were typically designed for teams of students, encouraging them to work together to achieve common goals. Team members had shared responsibilities, requiring them to coordinate their efforts and contribute to the project's success. Students provided feedback to each other, offering constructive criticism and support, fostering a culture of learning and improvement.

4. 21st Century: PBL for the Digital Age

PBL in the 21st century emphasizes the development of 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, collaboration, and creativity. Projects are increasingly designed to address real-world challenges, connecting learning to current events and global issues. PBL is being adapted to support personalized learning, allowing students to pursue their own interests and learning styles. This period is highlighted as the era where PBL truly embraced the digital age. This has led to a dynamic evolution of PBL, incorporating new technologies and addressing the needs of a rapidly changing world.

Technology has become an essential tool in PBL, enabling students to research, collaborate, create, and share their work in innovative ways. PBL projects now often leverage digital platforms like Google Classroom, Canva, and online research databases, providing students with access to a wealth of information and resources. Students can create multimedia projects, incorporating video, audio, graphics, and interactive elements, enhancing their learning experience and demonstrating their understanding in engaging ways. PBL projects now emphasize digital literacy, equipping students with the skills they need to navigate the digital world effectively. PBL projects often involve tackling real-world problems with a digital focus, encouraging students to analyze data, evaluate information, and develop solutions using technology. Digital tools facilitate communication and collaboration, allowing students to work together on projects regardless of location, fostering global perspectives and teamwork.

The Future of PBL

PBL continues to evolve, driven by advancements in technology, changing educational philosophies, and the ever-changing needs of the workforce. The future of PBL will likely focus on empowering students to take ownership of their learning, become active participants in their education, and contribute to their communities. PBL will likely be integrated with other innovative approaches, such as blended learning, gamification, and maker spaces, to create a more dynamic and engaging learning experience.

The development of PBL has been a journey of continuous improvement, reflecting the evolving needs of learners and the changing landscape of education. It's a testament to the power of hands-on, inquiry-based learning and its potential to prepare students for success in the 21st century.

CONCLUSION

PBL continues to evolve, adapting to the changing needs of educators and students. As technology advances and the world becomes more interconnected, PBL will continue to be a valuable approach to learning, preparing students to be active, engaged, and successful citizens of the 21st century.

It's been a fascinating journey to trace the development of PBL. Its evolution reflects the changing landscape of education and the ever-evolving needs of learners. As we move forward, PBL will continue to be a dynamic and innovative approach to learning, shaping the future of education and empowering students to thrive in a complex and interconnected world.

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